

Celebrity Endorsement and Consumption Behavior: A Case Study of Lahore, Pakistan

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Abstract

The marketing techniques in developing countries have changed a lot since the start of this century. The concept of branding have given new imputes to these marketing techniques. The role of celebrates from different fields play significant role in changing consumer buying behavior. The present study has been designed to check how celebrity endorsement affects the consumer buying behavior. A questionnaire was developed to realize the objective of the study for the people of Lahore. The data is collected through paper pencil method from two shopping malls namely Emporium mall and Packages mall. A total of 256 respondents participated in the survey. Higher order CFA was used to measure celebrity endorsement variable with the help of four first order latent variables namely personal traits, credibility of the endorsement, brand credibility, and ad recall. SEM was applied to see the impact of celebrity endorsement on buying behavior of the consumers. The results of the study showed that four latent variables are measuring the concept of celebrity endorsement. Furthermore, the results also confirmed that celebrities appearing in Ads significantly affect the consumer buying behavior.

Key Words: Consumer behavior, Celebrity Endorsement, Confirmatory Factor Analysis, Structural Equation Modeling

1. Introduction

The advancement in technology has brought a revolution in marketing methods. Today, seller prefers digital marketing to the traditional newspaper marketing (Munshi & Munshi, 2012). Moreover, the concept of branding evolved at the end of the last century, and the appearance of celebrities in branded goods has increased significantly (Ladhari, Massa, & Skandrani, 2020). Technological innovation has brought about a significant transition, such as the perception that a brand's potential to provide excellent customer service and support is reasonably caused by brand endorsement. Technology has transformed marketing by making campaigns more personalized and engaging for consumers and providing more linked and tailored ecosystems for marketers. The present study is designed to see how celebrity endorsement in ads (both TV and internet sources) of branded clothes changes consumers' buying behavior.

The main goal of ads is to intrigue the consumer and entice them to purchase the product. The firms utilize their resources to attract customers to their products or service through various advertising methods. According to Ohanian (1990), advertising is used by nearly every firm in a wide range of industries to promote their products and services since it is the most successful and efficient way of reaching a big audience. A brand is not only a name or a symbol but is much more than that. Branding is the product's overall image; it is the tool that connects the customer's heart and mind (Silvera & Austad, 2004). The role of celebrities has increased to target the market, emotional attachment, and build loyalty (Kim et al., 2020).

The choice of celebrity for advertisement is always an important step for the wide recognition of the brands. Celebrities not only attract consumers towards a certain brand but they also develop trust of the consumer towards a particular brand. The favorable comments of celebrities for a particular product directly affect the consumer buying (Priyankara et al., 2017). Moreover, people believe they consume good quality products because of celebrity endorsement.

The current generation considers celebrities idols and wants to follow their lead and buy commodities endorsed by their favorite celebrity. In the realm of advertising, celebrity endorsement is regarded as the most effective method to attract consumers (NGUYEN, 2021). To make a brand effective, one must first understand what the clients want and needs and then offer a brand in response. Once customers embrace a brand, it thrives in the market for a long time, and customers grow more loyal to it. This strategy of integrating celebrities into the development of a brand is a winning recipe for increasing the brand's value.

One of the most common reasons for consumers' purchasing intent is that they want to be like the people they see in advertisements in terms of their personality and other desired features. Since celebrities attract more attention, ad recall, and loyalty from a large audience, they are commonly employed in advertising campaigns in order to enhance brand awareness (Priyankara et al., 2017). The physically attractive celebrity has a powerful impact on the buyers (Zipporah & Mberia, 2014). Furthermore, the confidence of the celebrity in the ads also gets attention and attracts consumers. In a recent study conducted by Li, Kang, Zhao, and Feng (2022), highlighted that attractive live streamers' greatly affect the live shopping. Furthermore, attitude of the live streamers is key indicator to influence buying behavior.

Certain factors, such as attractiveness, credibility, and congruence of the endorsers, significantly impact people's buying behavior. These celebrities not only affect the mass's buying patterns but also change people's choices in selecting any product. People are more drawn toward that product if their favorite celebrity endorses it. In a

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developing country like Pakistan, where many macroeconomic issues (inflation in particular) prevail, buyers are more drawn to brands that offer a good selection of clothes while not being too expensive.

1.2. Objectives

Based on the discussion above, the present study has tried to explore the factors determining the celebrity endorsement variable. After constructing a higher-order celebrity endorsement variable, the present study has also checked its impact on consumer behavior.

2. Literature Review

Now-a-day consumers are exposed to hundreds of different accents, tones, and visuals daily through magazines, newspapers, billboards, the internet, radio, and television. Marketers try to uphold their brands and entice customers to buy a particular product (Randhawa & Khan, 2014). The main focus of these marketers is to attract consumers and create pleasant associations between consumers and branded goods. Celebrities play a vital role in creating such associations (Bafna et al., 2016). Celebrities are well-known in the public eye for their credibility, attractiveness, or both. Advertisers use celebrities in their commercials to boost their effectiveness and believability. Celebrities effectively capture attention and favorable attitudes towards advertising when endorsing a good idea. Rajasekar (2018) found that influencer plays a significant role in advertising by altering the consumer's impression and attitude in the age of information and media explosion. It had become a common practice to use celebrity endorsement. Moreover, Celebrities extend their endorsement deals with brands to boost consumer purchasing decisions and market sales.

In this regard, Abbas et al., (2018) concluded their study that celebrity endorsement is rapidly growing in Pakistan and affecting buying patterns of people. Celebrities' likability, beauty, experience, and personality are the most effective components influencing consumers toward mobile phone purchases. Wadhwa and Chawla (2017) designed an empirical study to determine celebrity endorsement's impact on brand purchase. The results suggested that celebrity promotion impacts the viewers and is appreciated by the viewers. Additionally, it was discovered that celebrity endorsements of products and services positively impacted consumer purchasing behavior, elevated brands' social standing, and raised brand awareness. Furthermore, Boeing and Schurhaus (2014) determined the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase decisions in Brazil.

Celebrity endorsement improves product knowledge and raises consumer awareness. It is common now to hire celebrities to endorse various products. Randhawa and Khan (2014) found that celebrity-endorsed ads, comic character ads, executive ads, and fiction ads inspire customers to buy things. Marketers utilize celebrity endorsements to make advertising more credible and increase brand identification among consumers. Moreover, once the relationship between a particular celebrity and branded good is established, it will increase favorable fruits for the organization (Min et al., 2019).

There are many reasons why consumers get attracted to celebrity-endorsed branded goods. Consumers like the qualities of celebrities and trust their choice when buying any product (Erdogan, 1999). Physical attraction has remained an important factor in attracting consumers (Abbas et al., 2018; Ha & Lam, 2017; Hani et al., 2018). According to Ha and Lam (2017) celebrity endorsement has become a popular choice in advertising because of its distinctiveness and the celebrity's attractiveness. It has a significant impact on brand awareness and customer behavior.

Furthermore, Adam and Hussain (2017) also find out the impact of celebrity endorsement on consumer buying behavior. They discover how people change their preferences if their favorite celebrity endorses a particular product. The results suggested that the physical traits (attractiveness) and credibility of endorsers play a vital role in influencing celebrity-endorsed brands to alter consumer preferences. According to Audi et al., (2015), when choosing a celebrity, several factors such as brand credibility, celebrity attractiveness, etc. The study also concluded with the note that celebrity endorsement plays a vital role in altering consumer behavior.

The credibility of endorsers, credibility of the brands, and ad recall are significant factors that can affect consumer behavior in addition to the physical attraction of the endorser (Zipporah & Mberia, 2014). Hani et al. (2018) studied the impact of celebrity endorsements in jewelry commercials on consumer behavior among Lebanese women. The study suggested that the attractiveness of celebrity in ads, the credibility of celebrity, and Ad recall by the consumer are significant factors in changing the consumption behavior of Lebanese women. According to Khalid and Siddiqui (2018), the celebrity's emotional involvement, attractiveness, and credibility play a vital role in attracting consumers to a particular brand. Furthermore, Vien et al., (2017) found the impact of celebrity endorsement on brand perception and purchase intent related to the consumer. It was found out that brand credibility was the most crucial factor.

The literature suggests that celebrities have a very significant effect on the buying behavior of individuals. Many studies show how consumers tend to buy products if they find celebrities physically attractive and credible. Moreover, some studies have also shown that ad recall and brand credibility are essential factors in consumer buying behavior. The present study is a rare attempt to construct a celebrity endorsement variable by taking its four factors (discussed in the development of variables section) and then seeing that this variable affects consumers' buying behavior.

3. Theoretical Framework

Development of Variables and Hypothesis

3.1. Celebrity Endorsement

Celebrity endorsement is an advertisement method that makes use of well-known people to link their public personas to the companies in order to build brands' reputation. It is a useful tool for businesses that helps them to build a strong brand image in consumers' mind in comparison to the market's competing brands. In this study we consider celebrity endorsement as a higher order variable that is measured with the help of lower order variables namely personal traits, credibility of the endorsement, brand credibility, and ad recall.

Credibility of the endorser refers to the receiver's level of confidence in the message's source and the source's or deliverer's knowledge (Ohanian, 1990). AD recall refers to the extent the consumer to which he keeps the ad in his mind and how much he remembers about it (Hani et al., 2018). Credibility of the brand shows that the believability of the customer in the brand that it will deliver exactly what it has promised (Erdem & Swait, 2004). Personal traits include physical attractiveness, popularity and confidence. Physical attractive endorser reinforces positive stereotypes about them. According to earlier research, attractive people are more successful than unattractive people at changing opinions of the people (Ohanian, 1990).

3.2. Consumer Behavior

The phrase "consumer behavior" describes "the psychological and emotional processes and the visible behavior of customers throughout the search for, purchase of, and after consumption of a product or service.

Once a customer sees an advertisement for a particular brand, their attitude toward that brand is predisposed to either be favorable or unfavorable (Phelps & Hoy, 1996). Customers' attitudes toward brands are defined as their emotional responses to brand advertisements (Belch, 1982). Whether a customer feels positively or negatively, favorably or unfavorably, about a brand is related to whether they intend to make a purchase from that brand.

Figure 1 shows the relationship between celebrity endorsement (measured with the help of personal traits, credibility of endorser, brand credibility and Ad recall) and the consumer buying behavior.

Figure 1: Model to study impact of celebrity endorsement on consumer buying behavior

Based on the above discussion, the following relationships are hypothesized:

H1a: Personal traits of Endorser is a factor of Celebrity Endorsement

H1b: Credibility of Endorser is a factor of Celebrity Endorsement

H1c: Brand Credibility is a Factor of Celebrity Endorsement.

H1d: AD Recall is a Factor of Celebrity Endorsement.

H2: Celebrity Endorsement Significantly affects Consumer buying Behaviour

4. Methodology

4.1. Sampling, Data Acquisition, and Estimation Method

The present study is conducted to see how brand endorsement changes the consumer behavior towards the purchase of selected branded cloths. The present study is Lahore based (capital of province Punjab, Pakistan). Two famous shopping malls of Lahore namely Emporium Mall and Packages Mall were taken to collect data. The targeted population for the study was both male and female who are buying branded cloths namely Junaid Jamshaed, IDEAS, Khaadi and Sapphire. These brands were chosen as they usually hire celebrities in their TV Ads in Pakistan. Moreover, these brands sell clothes to male and females in the same outlets. A total of 500 sample size was taken to collect data. Five enumerators collected data in one round consisting of 10 days. The data is collected in from 1st of May to 10th of May 2022.

A questionnaire was developed to fulfill the objective of the study. The questionnaire consists of 25 close ended questions. The likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5) is used as measurement scale for the response. The total 256 respondent gave their consent and took part in the survey. The enumerators in

person collected the data. The reliability and validity of the questionnaire were checked before data analysis. There was no missing value in the data and no outlier response was found while screening the data. In this way 256 responses were used to estimate the model presented in Figure 1.

4.2. Estimation Method

The present study has developed higher order celebrity endorsement variable (dependent variable) with the help of four first order latent variables. These four variables are measured with the help of 20 questions while the consumer buying behaviour variable (dependent variable) is measured with the help of 6 measurement variables. First of all Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted to see how many of the considered measurement variables are measuring various variables of the study. The limit for minimum factor loading was set at 0.30 to retain a measurement variable for further analysis.

Structural Equation Model (SEM) is conducted after exploring the factors for latent variables by using EFA. SEM is applied in two stages. In the first stage, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is applied and in second the stage developed structural model is tested. In the first stage, CFA is performed to confirm whether factors explored during EFA are really measuring latent variables or not. Like EFA, the minimum factor loading limit while conducted CFA is 0.30. Various model fit indices are used to check the goodness of the fit of the measurement models. The fit indices along with the benchmark values are given in Table 2. In the second stage, SEM is applied to check the relationship between celebrity endorsement and consumer buying behaviour towards purchase of the product.

5. Results and Discussion

Table 1: EFA Results

Variables and Measurements	Factor Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Composite Reliability (CR)
Personal Traits		0.834	0.52	0.82
PT1	0.631			
PT2	0.707			
PT3	0.654			
PT4	0.681			
PT5	0.648			
PT6	0.606			
Brand Credibility		0.794	0.46	0.74
BC1	0.697			
BC2	0.618			
BC3	0.694			
BC4	0.560			
BC5	0.422			
Credibility of Endorser		0.723	0.42	0.63
COE1	0.740			
COE 2	0.436			
COE 3	0.325			
COE 4	0.643			
AD Recall		0.812	0.45	0.73
ADR1	0.352			
ADR2	0.713			
ADR3	0.736			
ADR4	0.576			
ADR5	0.546			
Consumer Behavior		0.813	0.55	0.80
CB1	0.588			
CB2	0.559			
CB3	0.738			
CB4	0.677			
CB5	0.737			

5.1. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

EFA was conducted in the first stage of analysis. Six measurement variables were used to determine personal traits of celebrity variable. Similarly, the variables credibility of endorser, brand credibility, ad recall and consumer behavior were determined with the help of 4, 5, 5 and 6 measurement variables respectively. Some of the measurement variables were cross-loading but we have retained them in the parent variable. Only CB6 variable

is deleted from the analysis due to low factor loading. In this way, all the other measurement variables except CB6 were retained for the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The minimum factor loading for a measurement variable was 0.325 and maximum factor loading was 0.74. The results of EFA are presented in Table 1.

The value of Cronbach's alpha checks the internal consistency reliability and its value must be equal or greater than 0.70. It shows that all latent variables have internal consistency reliability. The convergent validity of the latent variables is checked through average variance extraction (AVE) and construct reliability is checked through composite reliability (CR). According to Cropanzano and Mitchell (2005), the value of AVE must be more than 0.50 for convergent validity and value of CR must be more than 0.70. However, Lam (2012) highlighted that convergent validity still exist if the value of CR is greater than 0.60 and even the value of AVE is less than 0.50. The results confirm the convergent validity and construct reliability as the values of CR are greater than 0.60 in case where AVE is less than 0.5.

5.2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

The present study has developed a new questionnaire with the help of literature. CFA is performed on each variable taken in the study and then higher-order CFA is performed on celebrity endorsement (CELEND) variable. The CCELEND variable is constructed by using four latent variables namely personal traits, credibility of the endorser, brand credibility, and AD recall due to celebrity. According to Kline (2005), higher order CFA can only be applied when it has at least three first order variables and each first order variable have at least 2 measurement variables. In this study CCELEND have four first order latent variables while each first order variable has at least four measurement variables. The values of the goodness of the fit for first order CFA and higher order CFA is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Goodness of the Fit Results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis

	χ^2/df	CFI	GFI	TLI	RMR	RMSEA
Benchmark values	≤ 3	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.90	≤ 0.08	≤ 0.08
Personal Traits	1.871	0.986	0.982	0.972	0.027	0.058
Brand Credibility (BC)	1.016	1.000	0.994	1.000	0.017	0.008
Credibility of Endorser (COE)	0.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.000
AD Recall (ADR)	1.667	0.993	0.989	0.983	0.023	0.051
Credibility Endorsement (CELEND)	1.661	0.947	0.912	0.937	0.046	0.051
Consumer Behavior (CB)	1.991	0.987	0.985	0.974	0.021	0.062

The results of the study show that all the variables have values of χ^2/df less than 3. Moreover, the values of CFI, GFI and TLI, RMR, and RMSEA are according to the threshold level mentioned in Table2. COE2 variable is deleted while conducting CFA for COE variable. All other measurement variables except COE2 are retained for the final model as factor loading of all the measurement variables are higher than the minimum limit of 0.30.

5.3. SEM Analysis

SEM analysis is presented in Figure 2 and the values of all the fit indices are according to defined limits given in Table 2 except GFI. The value of GFI is near to minimum limit of 0.90. We can still consider this model is good fitted as the value of CFI and TLI are greater than 0.90 and values of RMR and RMSEA are less than maximum limit of 0.08. The detail results of SEM are presented in Figure 2 showing coefficients of different paths.

Cmin=354.189; df=219; p-value=.000; gfi=.897; tlii=.931; cfi=.941; rmsea=.049; rmr=.044

Figure 2: Path Estimates

The results of SEM show that the four indicators (personal traits of celebrity, credibility of endorser, brand credibility, ad recall) of celebrity endorsement have significant (at 1 % level) path coefficients of 0.83, 0.87, 0.94 and 0.92 respectively. Two measurement variables namely CB2 and COE2 are deleted to improve the results. These results show that all four indicators taken in this study are key indicators of celebrity endorsement variable. In this way, hypotheses H1a, H1b, H1c and H1d are validated. Furthermore, the results also confirmed that celebrity endorsement is positively and significantly affects consumer behavior ($\beta = 0.79$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$). The results also support H₂ hypothesis. The error terms of some of the measurement variables are correlated to improve the fitness of the model. The details of the hypotheses and related decision are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Tested Hypotheses and Results

Hypotheses	B	P-value	Result
Personal traits of endorser is a factor of celebrity endorsement	0.83	0.000	H _{1a} is supported
Credibility of endorser is a factor of celebrity endorsement	0.87	0.000	H _{1b} is supported
Brand credibility is a factor of celebrity endorsement	0.94	0.000	H _{1c} is supported
AD recall is a factor of celebrity endorsement	0.92	0.000	H _{1d} is supported
Celebrity endorsement significantly affects consumer buying behavior	0.79	0.000	H ₂ is supported

6. Discussion

The results suggest that personal traits of celebrity, credibility of the endorser, brand credibility, and Ad recall due to celebrity appearance in ads are key determinant of the celebrity endorsement. Thus, these results support first four hypotheses (H_{1a}, H_{1b}, H_{1c}, and H_{1d}) of the study. Moreover, the results showed that celebrity endorsement significantly affects the consumer behavior. The consumer usually tends to buy goods endorsed by celebrities (Boeing & Schurhaus, 2014; Wadhwa & Chawla, 2017). In a study related to Pakistan, Abbas et al. (2018) concluded that celebrities' likability, beauty, experience, and personality are the most effective components influencing consumers toward mobile phone purchases. Regarding brand credibility, Audi et al. (2015) showed it is important factor that increased lebanese cosmetic sector's demand. In an other study related to Lebanese women, Hani et al. (2018) concluded that the credibility of celebrity and Ad recall by the consumer are significant factors in changing the consumption behavior. The results of the present study are in line with the studies of Ha and Lam (2017), Rajasekar (2018) and Bafna et al. (2016) that concluded on the not that consumer behavior is influenced by the celebrity endorsement.

7. Conclusion

The present study is rare initiative to determine various factors for celebrity endorsement that in turn affect the consumer behavior. For this purpose, this study has developed a questionnaire consisting of 25 close ended questions. The data is collected from two famous malls of Lahore namely Emporium and Packages mall. Total 500 respondents were approached and out of these 256 respondents agreed to participate in the survey. There were no missing value case and after careful examination of the data analysis was conducted on the 256 responses. In the first stage of analysis, EFA was performed and measurement variables were explored for five latent variables used in the study. All the measurement variables were retained except CB6. In the next stage, CFA was performed and one measurement variable namely COE2 was deleted and then SEM was conducted. The results suggested that celebrity endorsement does play significant role in changing the consumer behavior. The consumers are attracted towards branded cloths if these brands are endorsed by celebrities.

7.1. Implications

The study's results highlighted that brand credibility and Ad recall due to endorser are two constructs of celebrity endorsement with the highest coefficients. It is suggested that these two factors must be prioritized while advertising by the marketing teams of branded clothes.

7.2. Limitations of the Study

The present study has taken data from only two shopping Malls in Lahore. Future research can be conducted if the researchers face no financial constraints by taking all the Malls of Lahore to generalize the results.

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Questionnaire

Please answer all the questions if you are user of branded cloths (Junaid Jamshaed, IDEAS, Khaadi, or Sapphire) and provide the best suited answer according to your opinion and choice.

Please choose one response for each question.

1.1. Gender: Male Female

1.2. Age: 18-25 26-32 33-40 Above 40

1.3. Academic Qualification: Intermediate Bachelors Masters
 Other, Please specify.....

1.4. Monthly Income: 20,000-34,999 35,000-49, 999
 50, 000 74,999 75,000- 100,000 above 100,000

	Personal Traits	SD	D	N	A	SA
4.1	Physically attractive endorsers make an impact on the purchase of good.					
4.2	Popularity of the celebrity plays an important role in attracting people towards a particular brand.					
4.3	Celebrity endorsers who are more skilled are considered credible.					
4.4	The power of the celebrity to influence others play significant role in attracting people towards a particular brand.					
4.5	Confidence of the celebrity affects the buying pattern of people.					
4.6	Celebrity’s ability to hold the attention affects the buying pattern of people.					
	Credibility of Endorser	SD	D	N	A	SA
2.1	Celebrity’s approach in advertisements affects buying pattern of people.					
2.2	Honesty of the celebrity affects the buying pattern of people.					
2.3	Sincerity of the celebrity affects the buying pattern of people.					
2.4	Moral courage of celebrity affects the buying pattern of people.					
	Brand Credibility	SD	D	N	A	SA
3.1	Celebrity’s credibility drives brand credibility.					
3.2	Brands hire celebrities for their increase in sale.					
3.3	Brands deliver quality goods if a celebrity is attached with the brand.					
3.4	Brands credibility is increased if a popular celebrity is related to it.					
3.5	People take into account the reputation of the brand before using a good.					
	AD recall	SD	D	N	A	SA
6.1	People often remember ads due to the celebrity appeared in those ads.					
6.2	Celebrity makes people remember ad often.					
6.3	That ad gains attention in which celebrity appears.					
6.4	The slogan of the ad is remembered due to celebrity appearance.					
6.5	People tend to remember at least one celebrity endorsed brand.					
	Consumer Behavior	SD	D	N	A	SA
5.1	People usually buy cheaper brands.					
5.2	People become loyal to the product if it is endorsed by their favorite celebrity.					
5.3	People tend to buy at product more frequently that is endorsed by their favorite celebrity.					
5.4	People become conscious about brands reputation while using a product.					
5.5	Buying pattern is affected by celebrity approach.					
5.6	People buy products under the influence of their favorite celebrities.					

Name (Optional).....
 Mobile Number.....
 Residential Area.....